

EMPIRICAL CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE MYTH

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ABSTRACT

This article seeks to make considerations about the myth and its need for application to learning processes. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it discusses a theme that is, at the same time, historical, classic and epic, in a way that is committed to clarifying its imposition on life and human existence since time immemorial. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it brings to individuals an entire aesthetic that contributes to keeping the Myth alive and thriving in contemporary society, not losing its potency, even in the midst of all the technical-scientific advances that have been experienced. This is a bibliographical research, based on classic authors who deal with the subject. The analytical-synthetic method was also used, as this is a resource that best explores the internal and external causes of the target object of study. The myth corresponds to that situation of response to what is carried as doubt about the existence, the being of things, the universal condition of natural processes that are beyond human comprehension. The Mythós were created from everyday experiences that were gathered for specific purposes, becoming necessary at each specific time. There is no way to analyze the present, you simply see it and store it for later interpretations.

Keywords: Myth; Mythos; Physis; Phylogenetic and ontogenetic nature.

APPROACHES TO MYTHÒS

Myth, whose name derives from the Greek *mythos*⁵, with a literary sense of historical narrative, belonging to the cultural tradition of a people, which wishes to explain the relationships between nature, men and nature, as well as those between men themselves through immeasurable cosmic forces.

⁵From the highest point of ignorance and disregard for the stories of primitive people, it was preferred to translate *mytho* as a tale, legend..., that is, a meaningless story devoid of any literary denotation (N. A). However, Mircea Eliade (1972, p. 130) argues that, "Greek culture was the only one to subject the myth to a long and penetrating analysis, from which it emerged radically 'demythologized'. The rise of Ionian rationalism coincides with an increasingly corrosive critique of 'classical' mythology as expressed in the works of Homer and Hesiod. If in all European languages the word 'myth' denotes 'fiction', it is because the Greeks proclaimed it twenty-five centuries ago." ELIADE, Mircea. *Myth and Reality*. São Paulo: Ed. Perspectiva, 1972, p. 130.

Using *mythos*, it was possible to transmit the deepest cultivated feelings, those that were *overvalued and, also, those that were undervalued*, respectively, in certain groups, peoples, thus inferring that it has, in its dynamics, an educational character, which disciplines conduct, at the same time as it acts as an agent of transformation. It is a complex narrative that, through the most varied adjustments, forms the condition of thought and culture of a people, so desired and necessary for the purposes of each social and temporal space.

Regarding the pedagogical issue addressed to the interpretation of the *Mythós*, the following example is cited by Byington (1986): “Parents teach their children what life is like, telling them the experiences they have gone through. Myths do the same thing in a much broader sense, as they outline patterns for the existential walk through the imaginary dimension. Using images and fantasy, myths open direct access to the Collective Unconscious for Consciousness. Even hideous and cruel myths are of the greatest use, as they teach us through tragedy the great dangers of the existential process” (BYINGTON, 1986, p. 9).

It is an intellectual construction whose origin is lost in the sands of time, because the form that has reached the present day has been modified according to the subjective interests of societies.

Myth corresponds to that situation of response to what is carried as doubt about existence, the being of things, the universal condition of natural processes that are beyond human understanding. Based on the explanation given by the *Mythos*, the individual can seek to achieve knowledge through the analysis of facts and phenomena, because they now have elements that allow them to distinguish one from the other. With *mythos*, men were only concerned with differences, whereas with Science, concern with differences and identities are placed in the foreground.

It is from the possibility of applying the intellect to the *Mythos* and its fields of action that the *logos* begins to manifest itself, and can much more be interpreted as the intellect *in action* with the aim of expanding knowledge, from the known source of knowledge, rather than reason overriding fantasy. Thus, the first philosophers created and developed the analytical-synthetic method from the systematic study of myths, causing intelligence to expand and in this process the emergence of new, more complex structures became necessary, because intellectual capacity advanced to others higher levels, demanding interpretations and syntheses about facts and phenomena at even more challenging levels.

Once Greek man had the opportunity to think, beyond his limited world and delimited by religious interpretation, he could never be stopped again, because his desire for knowledge tended to grow exponentially, no longer being limited to what was at hand. its reach. Therefore,

mythos could no longer satisfy his desire for knowledge and, even more so, it was necessary to ignore it, taking a radical stance against it, not for the sake of denying it for the pleasure of denial, but with the intention of expressing it . as an allegory, because there was an intense need to develop and consolidate a new form of doctrine with an epistemological character. “ For a Greek, a myth knows no limits. It insinuates itself everywhere (...). A reserve of thought, the myth ended up living a life of its own, halfway between reason and faith. .. Even philosophers, when reasoning reached its limit, resorted to it as a mode of knowledge capable of communicating the unknowable” (GRIMAL, 1952, p. 8).

When myths are taken as stories told to oneself, it can be inferred that there is an entire intellectual construction , based on the visual vision produced by the individual himself about what he created, in his imagination, for the object he focused on observing. . And, this invention has to be consolidated in *thought through concatenation* of the poet and his listeners to such an extent that it is real, even if only for them . It is an explanation, an affirmation of something that lies between the [*already*] understood and the [*still*] misunderstood, which makes it a scientific conjuncture. In this way, it cannot be a crazy explanation, because it must be convincing , easy to understand and understood by the majority, because if it were otherwise it would be denied and automatically refuted by the listeners, which would have the consequence of the downfall of the discredited poet. From this, too, we can conclude that the poet should strive to demonstrate that he was equal to the gift received from the muses.

Mircea Eliade (1962, p. 5) says about myths that “the definition that to me personally seems the least imperfect, as it is the broadest, is the following: the myth tells a sacred story; he reports an event that occurred in primordial time, the fabulous time of the 'beginning'. In other terms , the myth narrates how, thanks to the feat of Supernatural Beings, a reality came into existence, be it a total reality, the Cosmos, or just a fragment: an island, a plant species, a human behavior, an institution dog.”

Mircea brings a possibility of interpretation on how the unreal transmits the idea of the real, that is, the abstract, fantasy, applied to a phenomenon, through the intellect, makes it possible to clarify the occurrence of a fact. It elucidates the construction of a process, which occurred through the elements of nature, in its procedure of physical occurrences, long before human presence or knowledge.

Based on this explanation by Eliade, the *logos* precedes the *mythos* , because the chain of thoughts necessary to construct the plot of the *mythos* it required a broad load of abstraction and application of the capacity of the intellect on objective reality, in order to form the wonderful mythical world, with all its components and characters.

The *mythòs* is constructed based on the culture, facts and phenomena that surround it, leading the individuals within it to seek a *coherent explanation* for what directly affects them. For a long time, the mythical answers offered by the poems and demanded by their listeners served as value judgments about things, until the moment came when they no longer satisfied, because with changes in habits, the desire to be part of the polis, They lead a group to raise questions about the values that govern them and soon others join in, singing in unison and the complexity of the phenomenon has to be increased, so that its understanding becomes more difficult for man to assimilate. common. This was a thought implanted in Greek society late, because when Thales of Miletus, or Democritus of Abdera spoke, they sought to be understood by all men, regardless of their situation.

Even so, advances in interpretation are occurring and the capacity for synthesis, although still a little far from ideal, is already a further step towards processing what is represented. Hence, at all times, I argue here that *logos*, which can be interpreted as the application of the intellect to the phenomena of nature, in order to decipher them, make them understandable, does not arise with the intention of destroying nature. of the *Mythos* and overcoming them as if they represented a primitive state of human nature and that the evolution of man would go through the absolute negation of the entire historical-cultural body portrayed in mythology.

Believing in this, as an indisputable truth, is to ignore the entire phylogenetic and ontogenetic nature and much more than this is to try to deny the entire *Physis*, which represents everything that involves the human being in its constitution as a being of nature and that is not he finds himself reflected in it, not even when in the mirror of the water, in which, alone, he does not understand that it is about himself, depending on some other being to explain this phenomenon in which another [for him, unknown] is him and he is this other [*unknown*].

For many theorists and researchers, the emergence of philosophical-scientific thought in Ancient Greece (6th century BC) is seen as a break with mythical thinking, since reality began to be explained based on the consideration of nature [*Physis*]⁶. by itself, which can be known rationally by man, and this *explanation can* be the object of criticism and reformulation ; hence the traditional opposition between *mythòs* and *logos* . The first is something that is

⁶“*Physis* means dominant (current) vigor of that which sprouts and remains, in a constant sprouting and remaining and can be experienced everywhere, but it is not to be confused with the phenomena that today we call natural and gather in the expression nature. *Physis* should not be taken as any phenomenon, but as the being by virtue of which the entity becomes what it is and remains so, as long as its becoming (becoming) lasts, making itself observable as such. As stated by Martin Heidegger (1889-1976), when it was translated by the Latins as 'nature', its original content was distorted and its evocative force was destroyed” (IBAIXE JÚNIOR, João. The pre-socratic and the *physis*) .

protected by tradition and , as Nietzsche (1844-1900) rightly states, there is something superstitious about it , which leads everyone to respect its foundations as an act of unshakable and unquestionable faith, because, if by chance , if the magical formulas were changed, this would attract unpleasant things to the group, starting with the loss of divine protection or even arousing the wrath of the divine guardians. The second follows a linear process of occurrence where there may be changes in understanding about the observed phenomenon, but this does not cause things to change, making them fickle to desire, or mere helpless victims of some external force.

The myth helps to explain that the only part of the body, eternally impossible to be seen by the individual himself, is the face. You can only see it reflected on a smooth surface; however, he sees it represented as the opposite of what it really is. Alone in the world forever, without someone to guide him , to appreciate the phenomenal representations, he ends up like a wild beast stripped of cork, unable to appreciate the most perfect thing existence can offer him and thus, he falls in love with the very image he sees reflected. on the surface of the water, without, however, being aware of it.

The *mythos* about what happened is not a fantasy, but a fact that produces, as a consequence, a phenomenon that can be interpreted in time as an exacerbated love for oneself, simply because that is how it was recommended that it should be, but anthropologically there is an entire intellectual construction that shows man the dependence he has on someone who educates him, who teaches him to be a Being in nature, given the complexity that took over him, from the moment he becomes the holder of the ability to think and be in possession of abstract intelligence, that is, he became capable of creating something new, using his intellect and the experiences he develops.

What great masters presented and defended, such as F. Nietzsche, S. Freud and CG Jung, is that the entire powerful intellectual, cognitive and creative construction of the human being is based on a primitive structure about which very little or almost nothing is known. factual knowledge, because it is unknown what the experiences carried out by the first men were, in order to overcome nature and all its rudeness.

This structure needs all fantasy and types of beliefs , so that it can provide empirical and psychic support to the being in formation and who, even after consolidating his condition as an adult, continues to feel the need for such escapes from reality, in order to maintain be emotionally balanced.

Taking the above, one comes to the conclusion that the myth corresponds to a profound gnosiological construction, a very complex intellect-cognitive elaboration, which works with

diverse elements that date back to primeval eras of the human intellectual condition, however, capable of entering to man's psyche in its deepest nuances, making possible not only strategic control over other individuals but also over an entire group . But, still making their daily questions clear, why “ the myth attracts, around itself, all the irrational part of human thought, being, by its very nature, related to art, in all its aspects”. creations. And perhaps this is the most evident character of the Greek myth: we see that it is present in all the activities of the spirit. There is no domain of Hellenism, both plastic and literature, that has not constantly resorted to it. “For a Greek, a myth knows no limits. It insinuates itself everywhere (...). A reserve of thought, the myth ended up living a life of its own, halfway between reason and faith... Even philosophers, when reasoning reached its limits, turned to it as a mode of knowledge capable of communicating the unknowable” (GRIMAL, 1952, p. 8).

Expanding the concept exposed above, we have that *mythòì* they portray cosmogonic situations, involving conflicts and different interests in the construction, elaboration and expansion of values and desires regarding the object of interpretation.

The *mythòs* , as a construction based on experiences that men had in their daily lives , had the practical intention of capturing this sacred moment for ancient man and eternalizing it, not because it represented a fantasy, but to show those who would come after them as the gods were involved in political-religious decisions that were totally human. In Greek *mythòì* , the most important thing was human actions and not divine ones.

Even with a wonderful construction involving the phenomenal aspect expressed by silent nature, it is here that one can understand the mythological construction and all the power it holds over human beings, from its emergence to the present day. Ancient man felt capable of marveling at the phenomena of *Physis*; Thus, when describing them, much more than simply narrating them, the great Greeks such as Thales, Anaximander, Democritus made Science , to express what the act of abstract thinking represents, which, for these thinkers, was the ability to wonder. before the expression of reality, appreciate the glimpse, be ecstatic, because the experience and its effects on each being cannot be predicted.

For this reason, the *mythos* continues to provoke and awaken areas of the human brain, being described within a literary neutrality that the most fantastic modern writer has not yet managed to reach such a level of interpretation of his art.

The *mythos* holds such a dimension of charm that there is no one who reads or listens to it who is not forced, by the action performed, to issue an opinion and this will never be at the simple level of subjectivity, by extension, in an unconscious way , conducted to give you an

opinion, an understanding, a reading of reality, making some connection with some moment in life.

This empirical connection, awakened or provoked by the story, is a singular situation that finds no parameter in any other space of human existence. This is the reason that, when the *logos emerged*, it did not try to suppress the *mythòs*, as some philosophers (*sic*) suggest, who have no preparation and understanding of the cause.

The first logical thinkers, who took nature and its phenomena as peaceful objects to be analyzed, had to create a method of analysis and interpretation of what they saw and understood, before anything else, that the explanation for the phenomenon was a factor of limitation of it to that moment, with any and all manifestations being *a posteriori*, in time and space, treated under the same bias of superstition; however, it is the repetition of phenomena in other spaces, under other beliefs, or even under no belief whatsoever that leads scholars to seek forms of physical [*natural*] understanding of such events.

What is clear is that the basis for all observance, following a still archaic principle of methodological rigor, is the description of facts and phenomena in *mythos*, which proves their existence outside the world of imagination. The wise men who were outside the traditional religious establishment went on the attack against the priests and the first thing they decided to destroy were the bases from which they extracted their magical formulas and truths, through which they maintained absolute control over everyone. The mythical narrative itself already tells us that there was a very long distance between the first attempt and the second, the first being doomed to failure, because the insurgents tried to directly attack religion, in the case portrayed, the Titans, tried to overthrow Olympus and the gods, being easily defeated.

In the second attack, they used a more complex and bolder strategy, which was to destroy the bases of men's beliefs in the gods, because they discovered that what sustains religion is faith in superior beings and their abilities to respond to human desires and needs. Since mortals can overcome the challenges posed by nature using the fifth element, intellect, which once applied to the other elements allows them to develop means of overcoming their problems, the need to sincerely respect invisible beings will fading away until it disappears or becomes a remnant of a past with which the only connection that remains is through culture and tradition, a unique way of not losing the link with historical roots. This, the deepest and most unique function of *mythòs*, is to keep alive in memory the cultural legacies, such as the struggles, challenges, battles and constructions and deconstructions through which humanity found itself forced to go through in search of development, some sometimes alone, other times with the support of invisible beings.

It took much more than a little imagination to create the *myths* and the entire plot that surrounds them, because reference was being made to the way History itself could occur. What the overwhelming majority cannot understand is that imagination is a tool of the intellect that is always applied to the elements of nature, so that new, more complex constructions can be created, which become possible using the instruments available. , to create what you propose to create and modify.

For that exact historical moment, in which the condition of imagination was still rudimentary, the most that was possible to produce was *mythòs* which may not have been very attractive and the rejection of these may have represented a form of advancement in their poetic quality and as poets explored better forms of poetic expression for *mythòs* , they attached new elements and constructed narratives that made them more beautiful and charming. This already clarifies that the construction of *mythòs*, in the form that has survived to this day, he spent a huge amount of individual and collective experiences , applied to the observation, analysis, interpretation, understanding and synthesis of the events that marked the relationship between *Physis* and human beings.

There is no way to deny the relevance of the intellect in the construction of all this, because otherwise, naively believing, even today, that fantasy and imagination are forces that act in isolation and even contrary to epistemic development, humanity would remain infantilized, being guided by a very few beings who dared to ignore the two enchanting forces of life, surrendering themselves solely to the power of the intellect, completely ignoring the reason given by experience. Neither group would prove capable of surviving for too long; the first would be nothing more than imbeciles, not realizing the real dangers of nature that surrounded them and the second group would be nothing more than sociopaths and psychopaths, since the denial of fantasy leads to discomfort and serious brain disorders that are denied by the crazy person. dominated exclusively by logic .

The most interesting thing about the interpretative study of *mythòs* is that it can be seen very clearly that they were all constructed considering the *psychology of the object* ⁷, that is, human beings at that historical moment were creatures who sought to live their lives in a more

⁷*Object psychology* is a concept developed by Professor Belarmino Senhorinha de Oliveira, during the production of his Master's dissertation in Education Sciences, at the Universidad del Salvador (Buenos Aires), in 2018 and makes reference to the elementary principle that each object studied has singular characteristics that shape it, according to the environment in which it is inserted and, thus, requires the researcher to understand it as possessing such elements, because its behavior, although it is supposed to be determined by the context, cannot be predicted with exactness (Authors' note, 2023).

Source : OLIVEIRA, Belarmino Senhorinha. *The theoretical foundation and teaching methodologies used by the teachers of the Nelson Mandela School - Complejo Penitenciario de Viana (ES/BR)*. Buenos Aires: Universidad Del Salvador (Tesis de Maestría en Ciencias de la Educación), 2018.

intense way and, with This demonstrates that they had reached the level of development necessary to understand the expression of reality with a veil of fanciful intellectual gilding, dominated by the imagination, especially because they did not have instruments that could carefully prove their suspicions about natural phenomena.

The moment he reached a higher level of instrumentality that could guide and sustain his investigative searches, he began to question the truth gained by *mythòs* , not with the intention of destroying them as is preached; but, with the condition of expanding the potential of intelligence to be applied to the understanding and clarification of the same phenomena that he had described in an elegantly fanciful way, in ancient times.

Even with all the controversy, discussions and dissent involving the myths, they survived the temporal action and all the didactic-pedagogical, paradigmatic , axiological and epistemological changes to which they were subjected in modern societies. This condition is possibly due to the fact that human thought, in its primordial condition, continues to follow the same principles from time immemorial. Consciously, it can be believed that the human race has greatly improved its intellect-cognitive capacity, but in short, it has become very evident that each time has produced men of superior intellectual genius, but who have not been able to think and develop processes. creative far beyond the axiological values and technological conditions available in their respective times.

The Greeks were excellent speakers and cultivated this quality, which was so refined among them that it took on the appearance of an innate condition. It can be assumed that it was from the systematization of politics that such a need arose among them. They thus developed a whole set of verbal techniques capable of facilitating the understanding and accommodation of thoughts and word games placed in space by the poet. They accomplished such a linguistic feat because “for the Greeks of Classical Antiquity, the *myth* was a true narrative, as they trusted the *poet-rhapsode (the narrator)*. They believed that the poet was one of those chosen by the gods who confided in him past events and allowed him to visualize the origin of beings and all things. The gods did so , so that the poet could convey the true facts to humans. The basic function of myth was to reassure men in the face of an unknown and frightening world. Just as they turned to the gods to alleviate their affliction, they also turned to myths” (RICARDO, 2022, p. 7), so that the mythical narrative functioned as an elixir for the doubts that haunted everyone and, with this, they managed to to appease human curiosity. This was enough, because there was no need for anything else, since this was spoken through the mouths of the muses. The entire cadence, organization and arrangements used to present the adventures of the heroes

were so enlightening that they were , in themselves, capable of appeasing the desire for knowledge that has been burning and governing the human soul since the earliest times.

Once again, it is necessary to clarify that, when stating that the classical Greek considered mythical narration as a true story, this concept was linked to the fact that it expressed a memory of a heroic deed that represented a sense of immense value for that person . people. There they were brought to memory, the protective god, the protective warrior, the manes, all being remembered for their immeasurable role in the perpetuation of that community. This is the sacred meaning of myth for the Greek people of Antiquity.

There was much more than a sacred meaning contained in the story, it expressed and transmitted this condition to the listeners, perpetuating the truth, clarifying the doubts posed by existence and especially, by the confrontation with the phenomena that crossed it in a bold, heavy and excessive way. .

The analysis and interpretation of myths makes it possible to understand cultural changes and an understanding of the historical condition of humanity regarding its rites, customs and even how barbaric and cruel forms of marriage unions and other consecrations were interrupted, causing the entire society change their way of being and thinking, enabling the birth of delicate forms of consummation of gamic contracts.

For a long time, in human history, the answers to all doubts, such as the education of children, respect for the elderly, the conquest of geographic space in the midst of severe struggles and bloody battles against monstrous adversaries and, above all, measures to live decently in society, avoiding the blows and traps set by life, came through oracles and *mythói* .

It represented a significant loss, the conversion of the interpretation of *mythos* to a mere fantasy of backward and ignorant, superstitious people and that such stories had nothing to do with the objective reality in which all those figures were inserted who, from the intellectualized and superior world view of contemporary times, were nothing more than beasts wild and primitive.

Greco-Roman culture , because the sophists and philosophers of Antiquity [*and even serious scholars of later eras*] maintained a deep respect for *mythos*. and its relevance for the integral formation of the human personological structure and the understanding of the history of the beginning of human civilization.

The most interesting thing is that this herculean proposal and effort to destroy popular, religious and poetic tales befell Greece and the *mithòi* of the Arab peoples continued to be portrayed as *tales*, an integral part of their culture and as for the Egyptians, it is their *history*. Only to *mithòi* Greeks were given a title whose translation is linked to *fantasy*, *fertile*

imagination, madness, lie [Why is that?]. Applying the same poison to the Latins, Christians who adhere to institutionalized Christianity destroyed the empirical aesthetic richness of the Greek *mythói*, and it is easier to summarize this attitude as a consequence of their envy towards the Greeks, whom they never managed to surpass on a cultural level, even Italy being mistress of a Virgil (70 ane-19 adne); Ovid (43 ane-18 dne); a Dante Alighieri (1265-1321); Donatello (1386-1466); Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519); Michelangelo Buonarroti (1475-1564); Rafael Sanzio (1483-1520); a Giuseppe Tartini (1692-1770) and all the unparalleled and unsurpassable creations of these masters. The problem is not in having produced works as important and rare as their thinkers and everything they left as an intellectual heritage; the issue is not having been able to overcome them. For example, Protagoras of Abdera and Democritus of Abdera were infinitely superior to the Athenian priestly triad: Socrates, Plato and Aristotle; However, Christianity spent more than 2000 years destroying their books and dirtying their names.

But it wasn't poetry pure and simple that enchanted; it was its representative set that exercised the fascination, linked to the fact that "poetry for the ancient Greek meant a gift granted by the Muses; a grace from the gods. Being the result of divine inspiration, poetry, therefore, was external to the poet, a vision quite different from the one we have today, whose driving cell of creation would be the gushing of the artist's own subjectivity ; The poet was also seen as a master of truth. This is because the Muses, who would breathe the words of wisdom, would be daughters of Memory, a religious power linked to Truth, [*clarifying that*] truth for the Greeks did not mean the opposite of lies, as it is in our society.

Truth (*Alétheia*) was the opposite of Oblivion (*Léthe*) , while *Alétheia* gives brightness and splendor , *Léthe* brings silence and obscurity . The high honor in archaic society was to be immortalized by the poet's words [*in his poetry*] . [*These*] are indisputable words, therefore, true. The 'sung word' has the power to engender itself in the collective memory of the people, being transmitted through generations as a real and deep source of knowledge of what was, is and will be. At this moment, according to Plato, the poet was deprived of all his feelings, and Reason was completely suppressed." In this vision, this divine privilege was intended only for initiates, since to achieve it there was a need to leave oneself, to provoke a state of ecstasy; This is because the priest Plato hated the people, which led him to create an exclusivist religion for his initiates .

Plato, who was not so attached to religious precepts and, paradoxically, he represented the prototype of the priest for centuries to come, because it was he who instituted monotheism, dogmatism, intolerance, the burning of books and enemies: this was the heritage he left for us . However, when taking the first and very relevant steps towards understanding human

psychological behavior, in different stages and situations, you can observe that the singer - poet behaved as if he were completely alienated from the real world during his performance. It was as if the musicality presented had a morphine, anesthetizing effect on the audience and this condition spread to the spectators.

The Greek thinker does not clarify, literally, but exposes all the preparation, rehearsal and exhaustive training of the singer-poet, regarding the search for history, its analysis, his stylistic preparation and its musicians so that, during the performance, the necessary distance from objective reality was presented and this was introjected into the thinking of the Greek citizen as an achievable truth.

Reciting poets had great importance in the construction of Greek culture and its artistic aspects. These professionals, when seeking to expand their repertoires, also became great researchers, bringing other heroes, gods and creatures to the people, thus allowing the inference that “within this issue, it can be said that aedo, alongside the herald and the diviner, he was one of those responsible for transmitting the tradition, customs and, ultimately, the social formation of Archaic Greece” (LALÁ, 2008, p. 26).

“Nowhere else do we see, as in Greece, myth inspiring and guiding not only epic poetry, tragedy and comedy (and we would add lyricism), but also the plastic arts” (MIRCEA, 1972, p. 130). It was these men, the poets (aedos and rhapsodes) who gave life to characters who began to enchant the popular imagination and who served as an example, motivation and inspiration for warriors and politicians to this day, including, in this group, the pedagogues who became they would form after them, using different techniques, however, with the same fundamental element of preparation for the formation of Greek man.

Just as in ancient times, in modern Greek times “the poets went from city to city teaching men, in place of the city's old hymns, new songs that did not speak of the home gods or the Polish divinities; They sang legends of the great gods of the Earth and the Heavens, and thus the Greek people began to forget their old domestic or national hymns, replacing them with new poetry, which was not the daughter of religion, but of art and free imagination” (COULANGES, 2005, p. 378).

The aedos were professional singers of ancient Greek civilization; Their functions are not exactly known. Everything indicates, although imprecisely, that they were themselves composers and improvisers to the sound of the music of the harp (*phorminx*) and the zither (*kitharis*). What fundamentally distinguishes rhapsodes from aedos is that the former have no role in creation or improvisation. They are reciters (and no longer singers) of other people's

works, disseminating them and ensuring their posterity. They moved from land to land in order to participate in festivals.

Possibly, the aedos were more linked to the times when religion dominated the context of politics and determined the entire social set-up of Greece. With the change in concepts, they disappeared and gave way to a new type of poetic expression that was less linked to the usual customs of the people. The *mythòì* they persisted, however, now subject to new interpretations and understandings.

This condition of overcoming strict human feeling, reaching the point of enchanting, as if by magic, was a gift from the Masses, that only one human being, in particular, had had the honor of receiving such praise, which was Sappho, from Lesbos., the poet called by Plato *the Tenth Muse*, so high was her level of expression of poetic art (RIBEIRO JR., 2003).

Plato will criticize the tragic artists for their proximity to the Stratego of the City and for the fact that they wrote their works in a way that kept the social order under strict control. Plato criticized poetry for despairing in the face of the mutability of life, which is why he created *kallipolis* as an ideal of perfection – perfection for the Greek was eternal immutability. He realized very well how much art had the power to change the psychological structures of human beings and later, F. Nietzsche would distill his medicine against theater because of this condition of massification, which was understood as a way of equalizing human perceptions [*or non-perceptions*] about things that exist and that exert an absurd weight on everyone, without distinction.

Such was the consideration given to the form of contemplation offered by the gods to the *aedo* and the *rhapsode*, that Plato went so far as to say that “the poet is a light, winged, sacred thing and cannot create before feeling inspiration, being outside of itself and losing the use of Reason. Until he receives this divine gift, no human being is capable of writing verses or uttering oracles. [*Therefore*], (...) it is by a divine privilege that good poets are the interpreters of the gods” (1988, p. 55).

Analyzing the continuation of this quote, Plato makes it very clear that he is not paying a compliment, but an insult to all poets, who do not use Reason to achieve knowledge, as they receive this from the gods: for him, poetry was a bad.

In Plato's understanding, expressed in the dialogue *Ion*, the poet practiced the purest philosophy, because he expressed all the wonder in the stories he portrayed, when he told the heroic deeds and made the *mythòs* take on an independent life, bringing everyone to tears, whether through ecstasy was due to the memory of a time that could no longer be lived by any of the participants, or simply due to the emotion provoked by the reciter's gift.

The Greek's passion for aesthetics was so great that, when an artist proved to be superior to their expectations, they said that it was as if the god Apollo Pythus himself was there reciting the poem through the mouth of the *aedo*. The *aedo* was compared to the god, who was unsurpassed in his art, which is understood here as technique.

What happens is that the Greek tradition was to listen to *myths* narrated from very ancient times. What he expected was that the oral representation would be expressed in a deep, transparent way, capable of allowing him the feeling of ecstasy. Good interpreters were difficult to find and there were no schools of speakers until those times and the Athenian curriculum had included the subject of music [*especially the lyre*] not long ago, and there must be perfect harmony between the musicians and the poet reciter.

The *mythos* told penetrated the listener's spirit carried by the beauty of the music and the sound of the poet's voice, as well as by all his bodily aesthetic art, expressing the feelings of the hero who denied everything else around him and the gods, revolting with This is your arrogant posture before them and your merciless destiny. There was a smile on the hero's face, showing a look of happiness, as if he were, even dead, mocking the gods and all their principles.

The *mythos* archaic brought all this intellectual construction where the hero was not frightened by his existence or his life, no matter how many challenges were placed on him. In fact, he expected more adventures to arise on his journey, because in this way he proved his value, for himself and for all those who believed or even doubted his ability to respond to the desires of the gods.

Much of what has come down to our days, and this is about trickery by priests, considering that it was these wicked men who adulterated the *mythos*, are constructions modified with the purpose of indoctrinating the faithful and strengthening the religious system and later, the system secular politician. It turns out that the original *mythos* appeared many centuries before writing arrived in Greece, therefore, they belonged to the oral tradition, in which an entire costume was used as a formal element for the purposes for which they were intended.

The moment graphic expression becomes part of the recording system of the religious scope, the texts that are being recorded are adapted to meet a new order of thought and thus lose a significant part of their original structuring in which the The hero was an independent being, facing the challenges of wild nature alone. From now on, there are gods who control all the weather and use them to punish men and the poet highlights this presence of divinity, with all the pomp and glory that is due to him.

In the dialogue *Ion*, Plato expresses the idea explained above profoundly well: “(...) it seems to me that the divinity shows us clearly, so that we no longer hesitate, that all these harmonious poems are not human productions nor are they made by men; otherwise they are divine and created by the gods, and that poets are nothing more than interpreters of the gods, each possessed by whoever dominates them” (PLATÃO, 1988, p. 57).

In this, we see Plato, once again, showing his malicious verve, because all the Greeks knew that their *mythos* dealt more with human actions than with divine interference. Although the gods were constantly present in the actions, the Greeks knew that in the end it would be man alone who should decide, even Zeus made this very clear. Souza (1986) will state that, “The criticism of the Ionian philosophers was not, in reality, aimed at mythical thought, at the essence of myth, but at the acts and attitudes of the gods, as Homer and Hesiod conceived them” (p. 27).

This belief, in particular, would lead to the construction of birth myths, in which to enable that *poet* to be accepted by society and his writings, likewise, they placed him as having been initiated into the mysteries of some muse or some god. that was in that same line of defense of technical thinking. Like what happened to Orpheus who, despite being an unparalleled lyre player in history, the legends about him said that it was the god Apollo himself, a great lyrist who taught him the technique of playing the instrument and after he descended to the kingdom of Inferiors, learn from the great dead demons endless secrets that made their art truly unparalleled.

Orpheus' descent into the kingdom of Lord Hades and Lady Persephone is the result of a beautiful experience with hallucinogens and which was portrayed by poets as something fantastic, wrapped in a whole set of mysticism and the most enchanting constructions about what he saw and heard, nothing more than a journey into his own unconscious world and this enabled him to seek and find knowledge about his technique that, otherwise, he could acquire mastery, but which would take a much longer time. There was also the issue that Orpheus' descent into the underworld was seen as a challenge to the gods.

It was clear that he could not bring back his beloved Eurydice from the world of the dead and it was when he came to his senses that he understood that nothing he did would be at the level of achieving his intention, because there was no known drug for death. This will later be discussed by many thinkers, reaching the same understanding without, however, ceasing to treat mythos *as an experience, a pragmatic teaching*, such was the respect for the mythical tradition and its entire cultural composition and all its relevance in the formation of human personality.

The *mythói* they were at the fundamental basis of human history and not just of archaic religion or Greek civilization and this one in particular, due to the fact that the vast majority of what has come down to the present day came with the stamp and classic hue of this people. But, countless other peoples had their *mythòì tales* as a way of showing achievements and their respective traditions, as well as what could happen if they were not respected.

These *mythòì* were collected by reciting poets and decorated under the wonderful sound of the lyre, music, rhetoric and oratory until it became a classical tradition in Greece due to its charming power, and only much later, these texts are placed under semantic-philosophical analysis, in order to present what they held of greatest value for the people.

As part of the cantata it lost its political importance, it survived, especially after the emergence and officialization of the written tradition in Athens, the reading and the story thereof, which marks the emergence of the apothetic presentation of the Greek Tragedy, which, unlike the Comedy Greek, was faithful to the *mythòs* and its educational developments, a moment that survives in the show until the appearance of Euripides and his late plays, where he moves away from classical mythology and begins to implement dramas in theater and present on stage that are closer to ordinary, everyday existence. From a Nietzschean perspective, Euripides was the cause of the destruction of Greek cultural greatness when he allied himself with Socrates, in his fight against life.

This did not mean that the *original mythòs* ceased to be something relevant in the Greek life that was born, from that condition of transformation that was being imposed and, with this, it also began to have much less. This occurs as a consequence of drastic structural changes in politics and religion, allowing citizens to participate more actively in the decisions of the Polis and this puts them on a collision course with the need to think about more factual problems. They continued to think about these problems, so much so that man's condition was to be a politician. This condition disappears when Plato and his followers destroy politics and replace it with religion. After this tragic event, there was a shift in focus from one point to another; however, life as it had always been continued its march, with its poetry and needs for increases in happiness and social transformations, speculations and creativity.

When this analysis criterion is expanded to macro social groups, it is clear that there is a particularity of identification with the construction of an ideal that was surrounded by supernatural forces and conditions conferred on a single individual by a series of elements that are only possible in very peculiar situations and [*almost*] impossible to be reproduced artificially. Understanding, from the above that, arguing, based on finite logic, is an action that

requires a lot of time of cognitive training, purely abstract and conditioned to an end to which there is no coherent response capable of satisfying *Homo sapiens sapiens* .

Hence the *mythói* they manage to elevate the intelligible condition of the situations that surround people's daily lives. The explanation arising from his arguments does not require a high degree of abstraction, but rather a coordination of thoughts and intrinsic adjustments capable of fostering the polyphony of empirical possibilities that accompany the individual's existence.

In this same line of thought, the German poet Goethe expressed that the human being cannot be characterized as a rational being who feels, rather as an emotional being who thinks, considering that before Reason appears and dominates the human social condition, affective duty dominates him. In this sense, trying to consider the world from a purely logical reading escapes the logic, as is the case of dialectics, of the human individual as an individual who has an intrinsic , unmistakable world in need of explanations.

The *Mythós* were created from everyday experiences that were brought together for specific purposes, becoming necessary at each specific time. There is no way to analyze the present, you simply see it and store it for later interpretations. The closer you are to the object, the greater the fragmentation with which you perceive it; the more distant the fact, the better and more accurate the possibility of interpreting it, because the view reaches the object in its broadest dimension. For this reason, the tendencies will always be to see and perceive it as “(...) a game of light and shadow, discovery and covering, at the same time naive and complex, transparent and enigmatic [and] if its *contours* sometimes If they disappear, it is because they were incessantly shaped and remodeled in literature and the arts, each era molding them in its own image” (BRICOUT, 2003, p. 14-15) and in song.

With the emergence of logical thought, highlighting that the person who invented Science was Thales of Miletus, the person who invented Logic was Parmenides of Eleia, there was a break with ancient religion and not with *mythos* . This apparent split is due to the fact that both were very intertwined, but it was the first who depended on the second to exist and maintain itself politically and not the other way around.

The religious ideology behind the *mythòs* was to create a man who could appease the fury of the gods or at least dare to face them head on, as Heracles did with his stepmother, Hera. So there was a need for the mythological hero to be involved, in some way, with the gods, in order to be able to count on their protection in the most adverse moments. And the *polis* under the care and command of this divine protégé, was, through commiseration, also protected from Olympian assaults.

The sophists put such beliefs to the ground and once they disbelieved in the powers of the gods, they stopped even believing in their existence, which weakened the entire ancient political system, clarifying that it is no coincidence that the name of the city Athens is similar to that of their protective goddess, *Pallas Athena* and, with such action, they ended up leading the people to abandon old habits, including the appreciation of tales in which the adventures and misadventures of the gods were narrated.

The ancient Greek *logos* does not appear with the proposal to destroy the *mythòs*. There are many more elements that hide in the shadows of this puerile understanding. The challenge was to overcome the power of religion over the polis and the only way they found it was to destroy the only source of symbolic power that supported it.

The most rational explanations that were and are presented by Science are not capable of feeding the restless spirit and thirsty for imaginations, lucubrations, and the most diverse and, at times, strange constructions that the human mind creates and recreates in an infinitum of *ambivalences*. And this need is characterized as the main reason why the myth did not disappear over time and Souza (1986) argues that, “the famous law of the three units (action, time and place), although late in formulation, as a poetic theory, is present in classical tragedy. Such a law is not valid for myth, which moves freely in time and space, multiplying through an indefinite number of episodes”, in which its permanence in the collective imagination and in intellectual construction is noticeable in the various clinical treatises- semiotics, which seek out the first manifestations of the disorders and idiosyncrasies that plague humanity today in texts; These treatises were based on the legends and tales of the mythological era.

Christianity and the pseudoscience it invented are on the verge of destroying what remains of the idea of *Mythòs*; the first claiming that everything is just a farce, a madness; the other claims that he lacks the foundations of logic. Finally, both fight with forces too violent to destroy an immortal enemy; They thus become obsolete gladiators, fighting at windmills, because there is no way to deconstruct a power that is capable of feeding the continuous idea of a force that generates life and the meaning that it needs, in order to overcome the long path *obscura* that extends, *ad infinitum*, both forward and backward. In other words, it was not human intelligence who created the *mythos*, but rather it was the one who motivated and, moreover, allowed [*even going so far as to say that it forced*] the birth of other aspects of it, as well as expanding its capacity for deduction and synthesis. The entire intellect-cognitive capacity of the human being is limited to taking very narrow and small steps, when oppressed by pure Reason and/or by practical reason, what is and what is not is not and there is an end in itself, a faithful and correct determination that does not advance because it is trapped between

antagonistic forces. Thus, behold, *mythòs* frees human beings from their inert condition of being condemned to a tailor-made existence.

The *mythòs*, after the conception of *Physis*, comes to be compared to chaos, while this, in perfect contrast, is made with the substantial principle or primordial substance, the unique origin of all things (*the arché*). The first vacates on *Chàos*; the second in order, following an unquestionable metric and which, because it is ordered in a model that can be deduced from a Cartesian perspective, is capable of being observed scientifically and empirically, that is, everything follows a natural order pre-established by an invisible force. In *mythòs*, it is tangible, because the god or demigod determines that such and such a thing happens either as a beneficial action or as a way of punishing some human who has committed hybris, which made humans act *like* frightened victims of the gods and lived on the verge of placating and/or avoiding his fury.

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